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SYNERGISTIC EFFECT OF SYNTHETIC PLANT GROWTH REGULATORS AND MICROFERTILIZERS ON THE GROWTH OF CANOLA (*BRASSICA NAPUS L.*)

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Abstract

Synergistic effect of new plant growth regulators Ivin, Methyur, Kamethur and microfertilizers Rostok Extra and Radix Tim forte plus on the growth of shoots and roots of winter canola (*Brassica napus L.*) cultivar Sherpa was studied. Auxin IAA served as a standard for studying plant growth regulating activity. The highest rates of growth of shoots and roots of canola plants were obtained when the seeds were treated with plant growth regulators Methyur and Kamethur, or microfertilizers Rostock extra and Radix Tim forte plus, or a complex of plant growth regulators with microfertilizers: Ivin+Rostok extra, Ivin+Radix Tim forte plus, Methyur+Rostok extra, Methyur+Radix Tim forte plus, Kamethur+Rostok extra, Kamethur+Radix Tim forte plus. The plant growth regulating activity of Ivin Methyur, Kamethur and microfertilizers Rostok Extra and Radix Tim forte plus was similar or higher than that of auxin IAA. It was concluded that the synergistic effect of plant growth regulators Ivin, Methyur, Kamethur and microfertilizers Rostok Extra and Radix Tim forte plus on improving the growth of shoots and roots of canola plants is due to their auxin-like effect on the activation of processes of elongation, division and differentiation of plant cells, formation and growth of plant tissues and organs, as well as improvement of metabolic processes in plant cells.

Keywords: *Brassica napus L.*, IAA, Ivin, Methyur, Kamethur, Rostok Extra, Radix Tim forte plus.

Introduction. Improving the growth and increasing the yield of an important oil and biofuel crop - canola (*Brassica napus L.*) while reducing the use of environmentally toxic pesticides is an urgent task of modern agriculture [1]. In recent years, considerable attention has been paid to the development of new environmentally friendly plant growth regulators based on synthetic low molecular weight heterocyclic compounds, pyridine and pyrimidine derivatives [1 - 4]. The new plant growth regulators based on synthetic compounds, derivatives of N-oxide-2,6-dimethylpyridine (Ivin), 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine sodium and potassium salts (Methyur and Kamethur), were developed at the V.P. Kukhar Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry and Petrochemistry, of the NAS of Ukraine. Our previous studies have shown that the use of these plant growth regulators based on synthetic compounds, pyridine and pyrimidine derivatives, separately or in a complex with microfertilizers, improves the growth of grains, legumes and industrial crops, increases their productivity and their adaptive properties to stress factors of abiotic and biotic nature [5 - 9]. Thanks to the use of plant growth regulators based on synthetic compounds, pyridine and pyrimidine derivatives and their complex with microfertilizers, it will be possible to reduce the use of environmentally toxic pesticides for plant protection and improve the ecological condition of the entire agricultural system. Based on the data from our previous studies, the purpose of this work is to study the regulatory effect of plant growth regulators

Ivin, Methyur, Kamethur, used separately or in a combination with Rostock Extra and Radix Tim Forte Plus fertilizers, on the growth of shoots and roots of winter canola (*Brassica napus L.*) cv. Sherpa.

Materials and methods. The regulatory effect of synthetic plant growth regulators Ivin (N-oxide-2,6-dimethylpyridine), Methyur (sodium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine) and Kamethur (potassium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine), which were used separately or in a complex with microfertilizers Rostok Extra and Radix Tim forte plus on the growth of shoots and roots of winter canola (*Brassica napus L.*) cv. Sherpa has been studied. The compositions of the microfertilizers Rostok Extra produced by the LLC "Ukrainian Agrarian Resource" company and Radix Tim forte plus produced by the "Forcrop" Company (Spain) and recommendations for their practical use are presented in our previously published work [7]. Plant growth regulators Ivin, Methyur and Kamethur were synthesized in the Department for Chemistry of Bioactive Nitrogen-Containing Heterocyclic Compounds, V.P. Kukhar Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry and Petrochemistry of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine. The plant growth regulating activity of the Ivin, Methyur and Kamethur, microfertilizers Rostok Extra and Radix Tim forte plus, which were used separately or in a complex, was compared with the activity of auxin IAA (1*H*-Indol-3-yl)acetic acid) manufactured by Sigma-Aldrich, USA (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Chemical structure and relative molecular mass of IAA, Ivin, Methyur and Kamethur.

To study the regulatory effect of synthetic plant growth regulators Ivin, Methyur, Kamethur and microfertilizers Rostok Extra and Radix Tim forte plus on growth of winter canola (*Brassica napus* L.) cv. Sherpa, seeds were treated with microfertilizers Rostok Extra at a concentration of 100 ml per 1 liter of distilled water or Radix Tim forte plus at a concentration of 50 ml per 1 liter of distilled water, or each of the plant growth regulators: Ivin, Methyur, or Kamethur at a concentration of 10^{-7} M per 1 liter of distilled water, or a complex of each of the plant growth regulators Ivin, Methyur, Kamethur with microfertilizers Rostok Extra and Radix Tim forte plus used in the above mentioned concentrations. The treated seeds were placed in a thermostat for germination in the dark at a temperature 20-22°C for 48 hours. After this procedure, germinated canola seeds were placed in a climatic chamber, where canola seedlings were grown in a light/dark regime of 16/8 hours, at a temperature of 20-22 °C, a light intensity of 3000 lux and an air humidity of 60-80 %. The

growth parameters of canola plants (average length of shoots and roots (cm), and average biomass of 10 plants (g)) were measured on the 14th day according to the method [10]. Statistical processing of the data of the experiments performed in three replications was carried out according to the Student's-t variance test with a significance level of $P \leq 0.05$; the values are average \pm SD.

Results and Discussion. The study of growth parameters of winter canola (*Brassica napus* L.) cv. Sherpa proved a positive effect on these parameters of synthetic plant growth regulators Ivin, Methyur, Kamethur and microfertilizers Rostok Extra and Radix Tim forte plus, which were used separately or in a complex for the treatment of canola seeds (Fig. 2). The plant growth regulating activity of the Ivin, Methyur and Kamethur, microfertilizers Rostok Extra and Radix Tim forte plus, which were used separately or in complexes, was similar to the auxin IAA (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. The regulatory effect of auxin IAA, synthetic plant growth regulators Ivin, Methyur, Kamethur and microfertilizers Rostok Extra and Radix Tim forte plus, which were used separately or in a complex, on the growth of shoots and roots of 14-day-old winter canola (*Brassica napus* L.) cv. Sherpa, compared to the control plants

Statistical analysis of growth parameters of 14-day-old winter canola (*Brassica napus* L.) cv. Sherpa showed that the parameters of shoots and roots of winter canola treated with synthetic plant growth regulators Ivin, Methyur, Kamethur and microfertilizers Rostok Extra and Radix Tim forte plus, which were used separately or in a complex, exceeded the growth parameters of control plants.

The average length of shoots (cm) increased both with the separate use of microfertilizer Radix Tim forte plus - by 60.71%, and with the separate use of plant growth regulators: Ivin - by 44%, Methyur - by 51.43

%, Kamethur - by 62%, and also with the use of plant growth regulators in a complex with microfertilizers: Ivin+Radix Tim forte plus - by 24.29%, Methyur+Radix Tim forte plus - by 17.55%, Methyur+Rostok Extra - by 136.57%, Kamethur+Radix Tim forte plus - by 80%, Kamethur+Rostok Extra - by 111.43%, respectively, compared to the control plants (Fig. 3). An increase in the average length of shoots (cm) by 40.26% compared to the control plants was also observed under the regulatory effect of auxin IAA (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. The regulatory effect of auxin IAA, synthetic plant growth regulators Ivin, Methyur, Kamethur and microfertilizers Rostok Extra and Radix Tim forte plus, which were used separately or in a complex, on the average length of shoots (cm) of 14-day-old winter canola (*Brassica napus L.*) cv. Sherpa, compared to the control plants

The average length of roots (cm) increased both with the separate use of microfertilizers: Radix Tim forte plus - by 133.68% and Rostok Extra - by 85.26%, and with the separate use of plant growth regulators: Ivin - by 76.84%, Methyur - by 147.37%, Kamethur - by 145.34%, and also with the use of plant growth regulators in a complex with microfertilizers: Ivin+Radix Tim forte plus - by 86.60%, Ivin+Rostok Extra - by 149.76%, Methyur+Radix Tim forte plus - by

161.05%, Methyur+Rostok Extra - by 203.64%, Kamethur+Radix Tim forte plus - by 173.68%, Kamethur+Rostok Extra - by 256.84%, respectively, compared to similar parameters of control plants (Fig. 4). An increase in the average length of roots (cm) by 78.2% compared to the control plants was also observed under the regulatory effect of auxin IAA (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. The regulatory effect of auxin IAA, synthetic plant growth regulators Ivin, Methyur, Kamethur and microfertilizers Rostok Extra and Radix Tim forte plus, which were used separately or in a complex, on the average length of roots (cm) of 14-day-old winter canola (*Brassica napus L.*) cv. Sherpa, compared to the control plants

The average biomass of 10 plants (g) increased both with the separate use of microfertilizers: Radix Tim forte plus - by 38.25% and Rostok Extra - by 42.41%, and with the separate use of plant growth regulators: Ivin - by 39.88%, Methyur - by 56.84 %, Kamethur - by 49.46 %, and also with the use of plant growth regulators in a complex with microfertilizers: Ivin+Radix Tim forte plus - by 59.03%, Ivin+Rostok Extra - by 48.47%, Methyur+Radix Tim forte plus - by

64.97%, Methyur+Rostok Extra - by 69.62%, Kamethur+Radix Tim forte plus - by 72.51%, Kamethur+Rostok Extra - by 93.37%, respectively, compared to similar parameters of control plants (Fig. 5). An increase in the average biomass of 10 plants (g) by 29.35% compared to the control plants was also observed under the regulatory effect of auxin IAA (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. The regulatory effect of auxin IAA, synthetic plant growth regulators Ivin, Methyur, Kamethur and microfertilizers Rostok Extra and Radix Tim forte plus, which were used separately or in a complex, on the average biomass of 10 plants (g) of 14-day-old winter canola (*Brassica napus L.*) cv. Sherpa, compared to the control plants

Summarizing the obtained data, it should be noted that the highest growth parameters of winter canola (*Brassica napus L.*) cv. Sherpa were obtained when the seeds were treated with synthetic plant growth regulators Methyur and Kamethur, or microfertilizers Rostok extra and Radix Tim forte plus, or a complex of plant growth regulators with microfertilizers: Ivin+Rostok extra, Ivin+Radix Tim forte plus, Methyur+Rostok extra, Methyur+Radix Tim forte plus, Kamethur+Rostok extra, Kamethur+Radix Tim forte plus. The regulatory effect of the synthetic plant growth regulators Ivin, Methyur, Kamethur and microfertilizers Rostok Extra and Radix Tim forte plus, which were used separately or in complexes, was similar to the auxin IAA, which controls the elongation, division and differentiation of plant cells, growth of plant tissues and organs [11]. The synergistic effect of synthetic plant growth regulators and microfertilizers is due to their composition. A plant growth regulator Ivin contains the macronutrient nitrogen; Kamethur contains the macronutrients nitrogen, potassium and sulfur, which are necessary for plant growth and metabolism [7, 8]. Plant growth regulator Methyur contains the macronutrients nitrogen, sulfur and the chemical element sodium, which promote plant growth and adaptation to salt and osmotic stress [7, 8]. Microfertilizers Rostock extra and Radix Tim forte plus contain macronutrients and micronutrients such as nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, magnesium, sulfur, manganese, boron, zinc, iron, cop-

per, free amino acids, humic substances, which improve plant growth and metabolism [7, 8]. The results obtained indicate the prospects for the practical use of plant growth regulators Ivin, Methyur, Kamethur and microfertilizers Rostok Extra and Radix Tim forte plus when used separately or in a complex to improve the growth of shoots and roots of winter canola (*Brassica napus L.*) cv. Sherpa.

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